

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Modeling the Voltage Controlled Oscillator Using Augmented Neural Networks

Andrea Sofia Vallejo Budziszewski

Supervisor: Xavier Lizarraga

Co-Supervisor: Frederic Font

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Motivation	1
1.2	Objectives	1
1.3	Synthesizers	2
1.3.1	Basic Components of Synthesizers	2
1.3.2	Challenges and Limitations	3
1.3.3	RSF Kobol Expander	4
1.4	Voltage-Controlled Oscillators	6
1.5	Non-Linear Systems	7
1.5.1	Examples and Applications	8
1.6	Virtual Analog Modeling	9
1.6.1	Virtual Analog Modeling for Digital Signal Processing (DSP) and Audio	10
1.6.2	Virtual Analog Modeling for Synthesizers	10
1.6.3	Different Approaches of Virtual Analog Modeling	11
1.7	Neural Networks	12
1.7.1	Basic Components of Neural Networks	12
1.7.2	Basic Operation of Neural Networks	13
1.7.3	Feedforward Neural Networks	14
1.7.4	Recurrent Neural Networks	14
1.7.5	Augmented Neural Networks	15
2	State of the Art	17

2.1	Recent Trends in Synthesizers	17
2.1.1	Software Synthesis	17
2.1.2	Eurorack	17
2.1.3	Hardware Revival	18
2.2	Recent Trends in Voltage-Controlled Oscillators	18
2.2.1	Modeling Steady-State Oscillators with Buffers	18
2.2.2	Modeling of Voltage-Controlled Oscillators Including I/O Behavior	19
2.2.3	Behavioral Modeling of Drivers and Oscillators Using Machine Learning	19
2.2.4	Creating Behavioral Models of Oscillators Using Augmented Neural Networks	19
2.3	Recent Trends in Virtual Analog Modeling and Neural Networks	19
2.3.1	Virtual Analog Modeling of Distortion Circuits Using Neural Ordinary Differential Equations	20
2.3.2	Wave Digital Filters in Analog Modeling	20
2.3.3	Toward the Wave Digital Real-Time Emulation of Audio Circuits with Efficient Neural Networks	20
3	Methodology	21
3.1	Dataset	21
3.2	Feature Extraction	22
3.3	Dataset Distribution	25
3.4	Periodic Unit Model and Phase Integration	27
3.4.1	Control Parameters	28
3.4.2	Model Compilation	28
3.4.3	Hyperparameter Tuning	29
3.5	Main Neural Network	29
3.5.1	Data Preparation and Feature Engineering	29
3.5.2	Model Architecture	30
3.5.3	Control Parameters	31

3.5.4	Model Compilation	32
3.5.5	Other attempts	32
3.5.6	Hyperparameter Tuning	32
3.6	Implementation Details	35
4	Results	36
4.1	Dataset	36
4.1.1	Usage	36
4.2	Dataset	37
4.2.1	Usage	37
4.2.2	Correlation Matrix Analysis	38
4.3	Periodic Unit Evaluation	40
4.3.1	Model Performance Metrics	40
4.3.2	Validation Loss vs Test Loss	41
4.3.3	Actual vs Predicted Values	42
4.4	Phase Integration	43
4.5	Main Neural Network	44
4.5.1	Analysis	46
4.5.2	Analysis of the GRU with Z-Norm Normalization	47
5	Conclusion	50
5.1	Discussion	50
5.1.1	Effective Modeling	50
5.1.2	Model Performance	50
5.1.3	Phase Integration	51
5.1.4	Main Neural Network	51
5.2	Future Work	51
5.2.1	Fine-Tuning of the Main Neural Network	51
5.2.2	Real-Time Implementation	52

List of Figures	53
List of Tables	54
Bibliography	55
A First Appendix	58
B Second Appendix	59

Dedication

To my beloved parents, your unwavering support and belief in me have made every achievement possible. I am forever grateful for the opportunities you've given me and the sacrifices you've made along the way. This thesis is a testament to your love and encouragement.

To my cherished friends, you are my second family, always by my side through the highs and lows of this journey. Your friendship has enriched my life beyond measure, and I am thankful for every moment we've shared.

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This thesis is dedicated to all of you. Keep being such amazing human beings.

"the source of all is sound"

- Kabir

Abstract

This thesis presents a comprehensive study on the modeling of the RSF Kobo Voltage-Controlled Oscillator (VCO) using augmented neural networks. We developed and evaluated models to replicate the analog sound characteristics of the VCO, focusing on both frequency and waveform behaviors. A dataset comprising 437 audio samples was meticulously recorded and processed to train the models. Various neural network architectures, including feedforward and gated recurrent units (GRU), were explored with different normalization techniques to determine the most effective approach. The GRU with Z-Norm normalization emerged as the most reliable model, demonstrating superior performance across key metrics. Phase integration results confirmed the model's ability to accurately simulate the periodic nature of the VCO. Future work will involve fine-tuning the neural network and developing a real-time VCO plugin for digital audio workstations. This research contributes to bridging the gap between analog and digital sound synthesis, offering valuable insights for the development of digital emulations of vintage synthesizers.

Keywords: Analog Sound, Voltage-Controlled Oscillator, Digital Emulation, Neural Networks, Augmented Neural Networks, Phase Integration, Sound Synthesis, Digital Signal Processing, Music Technology.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

This project aims to model an analog Voltage-Controlled Oscillator (VCO) to capture and recreate the unique qualities of analog sound in the digital realm. Analog signals, with their continuous nature and inherent imperfections, add character and depth to sound that digital signals often lack. These imperfections, such as deviations and noise, are highly valued and challenging to replicate digitally.

In a world dominated by digital audio, there's a strong demand for the warmth and authenticity of analog sound. While many digital emulations exist, none fully match the tonal richness of an analog synthesizer.

This project focuses on accurately modeling the oscillators of a VCO module. By doing so, it seeks to bridge the gap between analog and digital sound, aiming to capture not only the frequency behavior but also how these oscillators respond to parameter changes and interact to produce unique sounds.

1.2 Objectives

The primary goal of this project is to develop an accurate model of the VCO. We aim to achieve this by first capturing the periodic nature of the oscillator. Subse-

quently, we will use a feedforward neural network to learn and replicate this periodic oscillation.

1.3 Synthesizers

The history of synthesizers traces back to the mid-20th century, marked by the pioneering work of individuals like Robert Moog, Don Buchla, and Alan R. Pearlman. These innovators laid the foundation for a diverse and influential field that continues to evolve today. Early synthesizers were characterized by their monophonic nature, analog circuitry, and modular design, setting the stage for the development of more complex instruments in the decades to come. [1]

1.3.1 Basic Components of Synthesizers

Synthesizers operate on several fundamental modules. See figure 1:

Figure 1: Basic Components of a Synthesizer

VCOs are essential to synthesizer architecture, generating various audio waveforms such as sine, sawtooth, and square waves. These waveforms serve as the building blocks for synthesized sound. By adjusting the voltage input to the VCO, musicians and sound designers can manipulate the frequency of the generated waveform. VCOs provide the raw sonic material that undergoes further processing and shaping within the synthesizer signal chain. Further information on VCOs, including their operational principles and applications, will be provided in Section 2.2.

Voltage control filters or VCFs shape the timbre of the sound by selectively attenuating or emphasizing specific frequencies within the audio signal. By adjusting parameters such as cutoff frequency, resonance, and filter type, VCFs allow for the shaping of harmonic content and the creation of distinct tonal characteristics in the synthesized sound.

Voltage control amplifiers or VCAs play a crucial role in controlling the volume or amplitude of the sound generated by the synthesizer. By modulating the voltage input to the VCA, musicians and sound designers can dynamically shape the loudness and intensity of the audio signal, allowing for expressive and nuanced performances. In simpler terms, VCAs help adjust how loud or soft the sound is within the synthesizer.

Envelope generators, also known as ADSRs shape the amplitude of the sound over time, controlling essential parameters such as attack, decay, sustain, and release. ADSR envelopes dictate how the volume of a sound evolves from the moment it is triggered to its eventual decay and release. By shaping the contour of the sound envelope, ADSR generators contribute to the articulation, dynamics, and expression of synthesized music.

Low frequency oscillators or LFOs modulate various parameters cyclically, introducing rhythmic fluctuations and dynamic changes to the synthesized sound. Commonly used for effects such as vibrato, tremolo, and filter sweeps, LFOs operate at frequencies below the audible range, influencing parameters such as pitch, amplitude, and filter cutoff frequency. LFOs add movement, texture, and character to the sound, enhancing its musicality and expressiveness. [2]

1.3.2 Challenges and Limitations

Synthesizers, while versatile, pose significant challenges. The complexity, especially in modular systems, demands a steep learning curve, requiring users to understand signal flow, voltage control, and module functionality. Maintenance is another concern, particularly with analog synthesizers, which require regular tuning and upkeep

due to drifting components and susceptibility to temperature variations. Moreover, the cost of high-quality synthesizers, especially those with analog circuitry, can be excessively high, limiting accessibility for many musicians and producers. These challenges underscore the need for dedication, technical expertise, and financial investment in navigating the world of synthesizers.

1.3.3 RSF Kobol Expander

Figure 2: RSF Kobol Expander

The RSF Kobol Expander (see figure 2), introduced in 1979 by the French company Ruben and Serge Fernandez (RSF), represents a significant contribution to the world of analog synthesizers. It gained recognition for its unique sonic character and innovative features, earning comparisons to the iconic Minimoog synthesizer.

The original RSF Kobol synthesizer, introduced in 1978, was inspired by the Minimoog but brought unique features to the table. Notably, the oscillator waveforms could continuously sweep, morphing from triangular to square to sawtooth waveforms. It also featured control via control voltage (CV) and gate.

The Kobol Expander, which is the focus of this project, was introduced as a rack unit instead of a keyboard, comprising all the modules of the original Kobol. Due to RSF being a smaller company compared to giants like Moog, Roland, or Korg, they couldn't mass-produce the synth. As a result, less than 200 Kobol keyboards and around 800 Kobol Expanders were made, making the Kobol both rare and expensive.

Despite its limited production, the Kobol was used by major artists like Depeche Mode, Peter Gabriel, and Hans Zimmer, underscoring its unique sound and influence.

Design and Features

Monophonic Architecture: Like many synthesizers of its era, the Kobol is monophonic, meaning it can only produce one note at a time. This limitation, however, did not detract from its versatility and sonic capabilities.

Dual Oscillators: One of the Kobol's defining features is its dual oscillator design. This configuration enables users to create rich and complex waveforms by combining or modulating multiple oscillator sources. The ability to continuously sweep oscillator waveforms adds further depth to sound design possibilities.

External Sound Processing: The Kobol's envelope and filter sections offer extensive sound processing capabilities, allowing for dynamic shaping of timbre and tone. Users can route audio signals through these sections to achieve desired textures and effects.

CV/Gate Control: The inclusion of CV (control voltage) and gate connectivity enhances the Kobol's versatility and integration with external devices and modular synthesizer systems. This feature enables users to synchronize the Kobol with other analog gear and sequencers, expanding its creative potential.

Legacy and Influence

The RSF Kobol Expander left a lasting impression on synthesizer enthusiasts and musicians alike, contributing to the rich tapestry of analog synthesizer history. Its distinctive sound character and innovative design elements continue to inspire artists and electronic music producers to this day.

Despite being relatively less known compared to some other synthesizers of its time, the Kobol's legacy endures as a testament to French synthesizer craftsmanship and innovation. Its unique features and limited production run have cemented its status

as a sought-after and highly valued instrument in the world of electronic music.

1.4 Voltage-Controlled Oscillators

The story of VCOs began in the early 20th century when Edwin Howard Armstrong and George Washington Pierce initiated their inquiry into the mechanics of oscillations. They used vacuum tubes for oscillators until transistors came into play in the 1950s. In the 1970s, VCOs were integrated into chips, revolutionizing their usage and making them much more common. [3]

So, how do VCOs actually work? They tune their frequency based on the voltage you provide. You can adjust the frequency of the VCO's resonant circuit (usually an LC tank) by changing the control voltage. The VCO creates a continuous waveform, usually a sine wave, at the frequency you set. It keeps oscillating thanks to feedback loops. In audio and music, VCOs play a crucial role in generating continuous waveforms at specific frequencies, making them essential for creating musical tones and sounds. [4]

VCOs have a wide range of uses. For instance, they are used as local oscillators in radio transceivers for wireless communication systems. They are crucial in cellular networks, Wi-Fi routers, and satellite communication for frequency synthesis. Additionally, they play a significant role in phase-locked loops (PLLs) for clock syncing and frequency multiplication. Radar systems rely on VCOs for target detection, and they are used in test equipment like signal generators and spectrum analyzers. [5]

VCOs are fundamental building blocks in synthesizers. In audio and music production, VCOs generate basic waveforms that shape sound. Musicians and sound designers use VCOs to craft a wide range of tones, from smooth and mellow to gritty and aggressive. The control voltage allows for dynamic manipulation of pitch and timbre, offering endless creative possibilities. [1] VCOs also contribute to various effects and processing techniques in music production, from modulating frequencies to creating intricate soundscapes. As noted by Chamberlin H in "Musical Applications of Microprocessors," [6] the traditional analog VCO module includes the

following output waveforms: square, sine, triangular, and sawtooth, but the RSF Kobol Expander specifically includes triangular, sawtooth, square, and pulse. [see figure 3]

Figure 3: RSF Kobol Expander's VCO

When evaluating VCOs in the context of audio and music, certain considerations are crucial. The frequency range determines the pitch and range of tones that can be produced. Phase noise significantly affects the clarity and purity of the generated waveforms. Musicians and sound engineers also pay attention to parameters like tuning range, linearity, power consumption, and frequency stability to ensure optimal performance in their musical setups.

However, VCOs face challenges in audio and music. Achieving ultra-low phase noise remains a goal for enhancing sound quality and fidelity. Balancing performance with power efficiency is essential, especially in portable and battery-powered music gear. Also, expanding tuning ranges while maintaining sonic integrity is a continuous engineering challenge. [1]

1.5 Non-Linear Systems

Non-linear systems are characterized by complex and nonlinear dynamics that defy description by linear differential equations. These systems are pervasive in nature

and engineering applications, manifesting in phenomena such as fluid dynamics, heat transfer, chemical reactions, and biological systems. In the realm of sound synthesis, non-linear systems play an important role in modeling and generating rich, dynamic sounds that transcend the capabilities of linear systems.

Sound synthesis techniques often incorporate elements of non-linear systems to create diverse and expressive sonic textures. By integrating components such as feedback loops, resonance chambers, filters, envelopes, and modulation sources, synthesizers emulate the complex interactions and behaviors observed in natural and engineered systems. Non-linear systems introduce nonlinearities, feedback mechanisms, and chaotic dynamics that imbue synthesized sounds with depth, character, and realism.

Feedback loops enable recursive signal processing, allowing sound to interact with itself over time, leading to the emergence of evolving timbres and textures. Resonance chambers simulate acoustic resonances and reverberations, enriching the spatial and tonal qualities of synthesized sound. Filters shape the frequency content of the sound, sculpting its timbre and spectral characteristics. Envelopes control the dynamic evolution of sound parameters such as amplitude, creating nuanced articulations and expressive gestures. Modulation sources introduce rhythmic variations, vibrato, tremolo, and other dynamic effects that animate and enliven synthesized music.[7]

1.5.1 Examples and Applications

Many commercial synthesizers incorporate non-linear systems to achieve their distinctive sounds. For instance, the Minimoog Voyager¹ uses feedback loops and over-driven filter circuits to create its iconic, rich tones. Similarly, the Roland TB-303², famous for its use in acid house music, employs non-linear distortion in its filter circuit, producing the characteristic squelchy bass sounds.

In the realm of famous tracks, non-linear systems have been instrumental in shaping

¹<https://www.moogmusic.com/products/minimoog-voyager>

²https://www.roland.com/mx/products/rc_tb-303/

iconic sounds. For example, the distorted, feedback-laden bassline in Daft Punk's "Da Funk"³ exemplifies the use of non-linear processing. Similarly, Aphex Twin's "Windowlicker"⁴ showcases intricate modulation and feedback techniques to create its unique soundscapes.

Non-linear systems are also prevalent in modular synthesizers, where users can patch feedback loops and complex modulation paths manually. Instruments like the Make Noise's "Maths"⁵ and Mutable Instruments's "Clouds"⁶ allow for intricate non-linear processing, enabling users to sculpt evolving, dynamic sounds.

By integrating these examples and applications, it becomes evident how non-linear systems have significantly influenced modern music production, providing tools for innovation and creative expression. These systems continue to inspire musicians and sound designers, pushing the boundaries of what is sonically possible.

1.6 Virtual Analog Modeling

Virtual analog modeling encompasses a variety of techniques aimed at simulating the behavior of analog electronic circuits using digital computers. It can be used to create realistic and expressive sounds that are difficult or impossible to achieve with conventional digital synthesis methods. [8] Virtual analog modeling has been applied to various types of synthesizers, such as subtractive, additive, FM, wavetable, granular, and physical modeling synthesizers, among others. Some examples of virtual analog synthesizers are the Native Instruments's Massive⁷, Roland JP-8000 Virtual Analog Synthesizer⁸, and the Arturia V Collection⁹.

Unlike their true analog counterparts, virtual analog synthesizers maintain oscillator pitch through digital clocks, rendering them impervious to temperature changes.

³<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mmi60Bd4jSs>

⁴https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UBS4Gily_nc

⁵<https://www.makenoisemusic.com/modules/maths/>

⁶<https://pichenettes.github.io/mutable-instruments-documentation/modules/clouds/>

⁷<https://www.native-instruments.com/en/products/komplete/synths/massive/>

⁸<https://www.roland.com/es-es/products/jp-8000/>

⁹<https://www.arturia.com/products/software-instruments/v-collection/overview>

They do not demand a physical oscillator circuit per voice; instead, they rely on virtual models or generator objects. This design does not substantially affect manufacturing costs, space, or power consumption. Additionally, virtual analog synths offer patch storage and MIDI capabilities, thereby enhancing usability and functionality. [8]

1.6.1 Virtual Analog Modeling for Digital Signal Processing (DSP) and Audio

In the realm of audio processing and DSP, VAM techniques play a crucial role in emulating the warmth, coloration, and nonlinearities associated with analog audio equipment. Through sophisticated algorithms, DSP engineers replicate the response characteristics of analog filters, amplifiers, and dynamics processors, allowing digital audio workstations (DAWs) and software plugins to impart analog-like qualities to digital audio signals. VAM for DSP enables the creation of vintage-inspired effects, tube saturation emulations, and analog-style equalization within the digital domain, offering musicians and audio engineers a palette of classic tones and textures. [9]

1.6.2 Virtual Analog Modeling for Synthesizers

Virtual Analog Modeling techniques have revolutionized synthesizer design, enabling the development of virtual instruments that faithfully reproduce the sound and behavior of classic analog synthesizers. By analyzing the circuitry and operational principles of vintage hardware, synthesizer manufacturers create digital instruments that emulate the oscillators, filters, envelopes, and modulation sources found in traditional analog synths. VAM synthesizers offer musicians the tactile experience, sonic richness, and expressive capabilities of analog instruments, with the added benefits of modern features, stability, and recallability. Virtual analog synthesizers provide a bridge between the analog and digital worlds, catering to musicians seeking the warmth and character of vintage sound synthesis techniques while embracing the conveniences of digital technology. [9]

1.6.3 Different Approaches of Virtual Analog Modeling

Virtual Analog Modeling encompasses various approaches to emulating analog hardware within digital environments. These approaches are often categorized into three main types: Black Box Modeling, Grey Box Modeling, and White Box Modeling. [10]

Black Box Modeling

Black Box Modeling is a practical and widely used approach in virtual analog modeling, especially for this project. In Black Box Modeling, the system's internal structure is not explicitly modeled (see figure 4). Instead, the focus is on accurately replicating the input-output behavior of the system. This method relies on empirical data and signal processing techniques to create models that respond to inputs in the same way as their analog counterparts. Black Box Modeling is particularly useful when detailed knowledge of the internal workings of the analog system is unavailable or when a simplified, efficient model is desired. [10]

Figure 4: Black box modeling

White Box Modeling

White Box Modeling is the most detailed and comprehensive approach to Virtual Analog Modeling. In White Box Modeling, the internal structure and behavior of the analog circuitry are analyzed and replicated using mathematical models and simulations (see figure 5). This approach aims to capture the exact characteristics and interactions of individual components within the analog system, providing the

highest level of accuracy and fidelity in the digital emulation. [10]

Figure 5: White box modeling

Grey Box Modeling

Grey Box Modeling strikes a balance between Black Box and White Box approaches. In Grey Box Modeling, certain aspects of the analog circuitry are understood and modeled in detail, while others are abstracted or simplified. This approach allows for a more nuanced representation of the analog hardware while still maintaining a degree of simplicity and efficiency in the modeling process. [10]

1.7 Neural Networks

Neural networks are computational models inspired by the structure and function of biological neural networks found in the human brain. They are composed of interconnected units called neurons, organized into layers, capable of processing complex information through activation functions.

1.7.1 Basic Components of Neural Networks

Neurons are the basic computational units of neural networks. Each neuron receives input signals from other neurons or external sources, processes them using weighted connections, and produces an output signal based on an activation function. The output of neuron j in layer l is computed as:

$$a_j^{(l)} = g\left(z_j^{(l)}\right)$$

where $z_j^{(l)} = \sum_{k=1}^{n^{(l-1)}} w_{jk}^{(l)} a_k^{(l-1)} + b_j^{(l)}$

Layers are organized into input layers, hidden layers, and output layers. Input layers receive external data, hidden layers perform intermediate processing, and output layers produce the final output.

Biases are constant values added to the weighted sum of inputs before applying the activation function. This allows neurons to adjust their output independently of the inputs, shifting the activation function horizontally. Biases are updated along with weights during training to minimize errors.

Weights represent the strength of connections between neurons. They are adjusted during training using optimization algorithms like gradient descent to minimize the error in the network's output.

1.7.2 Basic Operation of Neural Networks

The operation of a neural network can be summarized in the following steps:

Forward Propagation: Input data is fed into the input layer, propagates through hidden layers, and produces an output in the output layer.

Loss Calculation: The output is compared to the target output using a loss function, such as mean squared error or cross-entropy loss.

Backpropagation: The gradients of the loss function with respect to the weights are computed and used to adjust the weights to minimize the loss, typically using optimization algorithms like gradient descent.

Training: The process of forward propagation, loss calculation, and backpropagation is repeated iteratively to minimize the loss function and improve the network's accuracy. [11]

1.7.3 Feedforward Neural Networks

Feedforward Neural Networks (FFNNs), also known as multilayer perceptrons (MLPs), represent one of the fundamental architectures in neural networks. They consist of multiple layers of neurons, including an input layer, hidden layers, and an output layer, with information flowing strictly in one direction (see figure 6).

Figure 6: Simple FFNN structure

The operation involves forward propagation of input data through the network. The weighted connections between neurons are learned during training using the backpropagation algorithm, which iteratively adjusts the weights to minimize the loss function.

1.7.4 Recurrent Neural Networks

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are designed to handle sequential data, making them suitable for tasks involving time series and soundwave generation. Unlike feedforward networks, RNNs have connections that form directed cycles, allowing information to persist. This architecture enables RNNs to maintain a memory of previous inputs, making them powerful for tasks where context and order are important.

RNNs are particularly effective in synthesizers for soundwave generation, where the sequential nature of the data is crucial. The ability to process and generate sequences

makes RNNs an excellent choice for dynamic sound synthesis and modeling time-dependent audio patterns.

1.7.5 Augmented Neural Networks

Augmented Neural Networks (AugNNs) enhance traditional neural networks by incorporating additional information or features during training and inference. They leverage external data sources, domain knowledge, or auxiliary information to learn complex patterns and make accurate predictions.

Understanding Augmented Neural Networks and Periodic Units

Augmented Neural Networks process information through interconnected processes, beginning with a sequence of time steps (dt) fed into a periodic unit. The instantaneous frequency, $\omega(t)$, is determined by a feedforward neural network (FFNN) based on the control voltage (cv). The total oscillation phase, $\Phi(t)$, is obtained by integrating the instantaneous frequency over time:

$$\Phi(t) = \int \omega(t) dt$$

This phase is transformed into a bounded range using the modulus operation:

$$\phi_{\text{folded}}(t_n) = \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \omega(t_k) \cdot \Delta t_k \right) \bmod 1$$

The folded and normalized phase information is fed into the first hidden layer of the neural network. The hidden layer computes node values using a hyperbolic tangent function, and the output layer computes its values by summing the contributions from the preceding layer:

$$y_{\text{out}}(n) = \sum_{l=1}^{N_{\text{prec}}} y_l^{\text{prec}}(n) w_{\text{out}} + b_{\text{out}}$$

Figure 7: AugNN Structure

By integrating periodic units and their transformations, AugNNs effectively capture the periodic dependence of nonlinear behaviors in oscillators, making them powerful in handling tasks involving periodic signals. This capability is crucial for applications ranging from signal processing to time-series forecasting. [12]

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Recent Trends in Synthesizers

Recent developments in synthesizer technology reflect a dynamic landscape shaped by evolving user preferences, technological advancements, and market trends. These trends influence the choices made by musicians, producers, and manufacturers alike.

2.1.1 Software Synthesis

The proliferation of software synthesis solutions has democratized synthesizer technology. Virtual instruments and software plugins, accessible via digital audio workstations (DAWs), offer a vast array of sounds and functionalities. This democratization expands creative possibilities and fosters inclusivity within the music-making community. Software synthesizers provide intuitive interfaces and integrate deeply with production workflows, enhancing efficiency and flexibility in sound design and composition. [13]

2.1.2 Eurorack

There has been a resurgence of interest in Eurorack modular synthesis. The Eurorack format allows users to customize and expand their systems with interchangeable modules, fostering experimentation and innovation. The community thrives on

collaboration, knowledge sharing, and DIY ethos, appealing to musicians seeking personalized and unique sound palettes. The flexibility and scalability of Eurorack systems push the boundaries of conventional synthesis techniques. [14]

2.1.3 Hardware Revival

Classic hardware synthesizers are experiencing a revival, with manufacturers reissuing iconic models. These reissues combine the analog sound character with modern enhancements, appealing to both seasoned professionals and newcomers. Vintage synthesizers hold cultural significance beyond their sonic capabilities, serving as artifacts of musical history and icons of electronic music culture [15]. For example, Behringer has created a hardware copy of the Kobil RSF Expander ¹, bringing the classic sound to a new generation of users (see figure 8).

Figure 8: Behringer’s emulation of the Kobil RSF Expander

2.2 Recent Trends in Voltage-Controlled Oscillators

Recent advancements in VCO technology address both the technical intricacies of oscillator design and the evolving needs of diverse user communities.

2.2.1 Modeling Steady-State Oscillators with Buffers

Research focuses on modeling steady-state oscillators with buffers, which play a crucial role in real-world oscillator behavior. Neural networks trained on buffer-embedded VCO data enhance accuracy in capturing these effects, providing insights into buffer-related phenomena. [16]

¹<https://www.behringer.com/product.html?modelCode=0718-ABY>

2.2.2 Modeling of Voltage-Controlled Oscillators Including I/O Behavior

Extending the modeling scope to include input/output (I/O) behavior of VCOs, augmented neural networks consider both internal dynamics and external interactions. This results in more comprehensive models that aid in circuit design, optimization, and system-level analysis. [17]

2.2.3 Behavioral Modeling of Drivers and Oscillators Using Machine Learning

Yu's doctoral dissertation [18] explores behavioral modeling encompassing both drivers and oscillators, recognizing their interconnectedness. Machine learning techniques, including neural networks, offer a unified framework for capturing complex behaviors, empowering designers to make informed decisions during the design process.

2.2.4 Creating Behavioral Models of Oscillators Using Augmented Neural Networks

A data-driven approach proposed by H. Yu et al. [12] leverages augmented neural networks to create accurate behavioral models of oscillators. These NNs learn from actual VCO data, facilitating predictions of frequency responses under varying conditions. This approach addresses the limitations of traditional analytical models and accounts for non-idealities, offering a promising avenue for advanced VCO design and analysis.

2.3 Recent Trends in Virtual Analog Modeling and Neural Networks

Recent advancements in distortion circuit modeling have led to significant breakthroughs in audio signal processing.

2.3.1 Virtual Analog Modeling of Distortion Circuits Using Neural Ordinary Differential Equations

Wilczek et al. [19] present a study on Virtual Analog modeling of distortion circuits using Neural ODEs. Their models learn ODEs governing diode clippers, achieving performance comparable to state-of-the-art recurrent neural networks with fewer parameters. The models offer increased sampling rates post-training and provide physically interpretable ODEs.

2.3.2 Wave Digital Filters in Analog Modeling

Barrera et al. [20] detail the development of a virtual analog model of the passive equalizer stage of the classic Pultec EQP-1A using Wave Digital Filters. They show how Wave Digital Filter (WDF) models can be accurately prototyped in Python and then translated into efficient real-time C++ implementations. The WDF approach allows for the precise replication of the frequency response of analog circuits, maintaining high accuracy at higher sampling rates, and facilitating real-time operation through efficient computation. This methodology underscores the potential for WDFs in achieving high fidelity in virtual analog modeling.

2.3.3 Toward the Wave Digital Real-Time Emulation of Audio Circuits with Efficient Neural Networks

Proverbio et al. [21] explore integrating Wave Digital Filters (WDFs) and neural networks for real-time emulation of audio circuits. This approach enhances real-time performance and modeling accuracy, enabling efficient and modular modeling of analog circuits for audio processing and synthesis.

Chapter 3

Methodology

In this section, we describe the approach and procedures employed to model the Voltage-Controlled Oscillator of the RSF Kobol Expander. All the code and trained models can be found on the GitHub repository ¹.

3.1 Dataset

Creating our own dataset was necessary to train the models, as existing datasets were not suitable for our specific needs.

Our initial approach involved utilizing the DC Coupled Outputs of the Universal Audio Apollo Twin X² to control both frequency and waveform parameters. We intended to use Bitwig Studio³ or Ableton’s CV Toolkit⁴ to automate voltage adjustments in increments of 0.10 volts. However, we encountered issues: despite claims that all outputs were DC Coupled, only outputs 3 and 4 (labeled 5 and 6 in the DAW) functioned correctly but were inexplicably paired, preventing independent signal routing. Troubleshooting and UA Support did not resolve this issue.

We then opted to use Doepfer’s MCV24 MIDI to CV Converter⁵ for converting

¹<https://github.com/ObiWxnKenxbi/KobolRSF/tree/main>

²<https://www.uaudio.com/uad-plugins/apollo-twin-x.html>

³<https://www.bitwig.com/>

⁴<https://www.ableton.com/en/packs/cv-tools/>

⁵<https://www.soundonsound.com/reviews/doepfer-mcv24>

MIDI data to control voltage signals. Familiarization with its operation is detailed in Annex 2.

3.2 Feature Extraction

Control Voltage of Frequency and Waveform Knobs

We adjusted frequency in steps of 0.33 volts and waveform selection in steps of 0.5 volts.

Waveform Data

Waveform data was extracted using the `librosa`⁶, `numpy`⁷, and `os`⁸ libraries. This data includes details such as the number of audio channels, sample width, sample rate, and total frames. The raw audio data is read and converted into a NumPy array for further analysis.

```
def process_audio_files(folder_path):
    data = []
    audio_files = [f for f in os.listdir(folder_path) if f.endswith(".wav")]

    for file_name in tqdm(audio_files, desc="Processing audio files"):
        file_parts = file_name.split('_')
        if len(file_parts) != 2:
            print(f"Skipping file with unexpected name format: {file_name}")
            continue

        try:
            waveform = int(file_parts[0])
            second_number = int(file_parts[1].replace(".wav", ""))

        except ValueError:
```

⁶<https://librosa.org/doc/latest/index.html>

⁷<https://numpy.org/>

⁸<https://docs.python.org/3/library/os.html>

```
print(f"Skipping file with non-integer values in the name: {file_name}")
continue

file_path = os.path.join(folder_path, file_name)

y, sr = librosa.load(file_path)
data.append({
    'filename': file_name,
    'waveform': waveform,
    'waveform_data': ', '.join(map(str, y.tolist()))
})
```

Waveform ID

Waveforms were categorized using IDs based on their type, as shown in Table 1.

ID	Waveform Type
1	Triangular +
2	Triangular + Sawtooth
3	Triangular + Sawtooth +
4	Triangular + Sawtooth ++
5	Sawtooth
6	Sawtooth +
7	Sawtooth ++
8	Sawtooth + Square
9	Sawtooth + Square +
10	Sawtooth + Square ++
11	Square
12	Square +
13	Square ++
14	Square + Pulse
15	Square + Pulse +
16	Square + Pulse ++
17	Pulse
18	Pulse +

Table 1: Waveform metadata

Frequency Estimation

The frequency of a note is estimated by analyzing the audio signal using the `librosa` library. The `piptrack` function extracts pitch and magnitude information over time, focusing on frequencies between 20 Hz and 20000 Hz. The fundamental frequency is estimated by calculating the mean pitch values across all frames.

```
def detect_pitch(y, sr):
    pitches, magnitudes = librosa.core.piptrack(y=y, sr=sr, fmin=75, fmax=16000)
    max_indexes = np.argmax(magnitudes, axis=0)
```

```

pitches = pitches[max_indexes, range(magnitudes.shape[1])]
pitch = np.mean(pitches)
return pitch

```

Angular Frequency

Angular frequency represents the rate of oscillation of the waveform and is calculated by multiplying the frequency value by 2π .

```

def calculate_angular_frequency(frequency):
    if frequency is None:
        return None
    angular_frequency = 2 * np.pi * frequency
    return angular_frequency

```

All of these parameters are saved into a CSV file for use as a dataframe for the model.

3.3 Dataset Distribution

Uniform Distribution

The features cvfrequency, cvwaveform, and waveformID exhibit a uniform distribution, meaning every value within the range is equally likely.

Figure 9: Uniform distributions

Normal Distribution

The feature waveformdata follows a normal distribution, which is common in many natural datasets.

Figure 10: Normal distributions

Skewed Distribution

The frequency and angularfrequency features are skewed to the right, indicating a concentration of values towards the lower end of the range.

Figure 11: Skewed distributions

To achieve a more balanced data distribution, the Box-Cox transformation was applied to the frequency and angularfrequency features.

Figure 12: Box-Cox transformed distributions

3.4 Periodic Unit Model and Phase Integration

The periodic unit in the Augmented Neural Network (AugNN) converts control voltage (cv) and time step (dt) inputs into folded phases. This involves:

1. Calculating the instantaneous frequency from the control voltage.
2. Integrating this frequency over time.
3. Folding the resulting phase to keep it within a specified range.

Instantaneous Frequency Calculation

A model was created to accept the control voltage of the frequency knob as input and provide the angular frequency as output. This model is integrated using the `PhaseIntegrator` class.

$$dt = \frac{t_{\text{end}} - t_{\text{start}}}{\text{num_steps} - 1} \quad (3.1)$$

Model Summary

Model: "sequential_1"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
dense_4 (Dense)	(None, 128)	256
dense_5 (Dense)	(None, 64)	8256
dense_6 (Dense)	(None, 64)	4160
dense_7 (Dense)	(None, 1)	65

=====
Total params: 12737 (49.75 KB)

Trainable params: 12737 (49.75 KB)

Non-trainable params: 0 (0.00 Byte)

3.4.1 Control Parameters

The control parameters for this study were defined based on the input data and the configuration of the neural network model. The primary input data used was 'cv_frequency', and the output target was 'log_angular_frequency'. The dataset was split into training and testing sets using an 80-20 ratio.

- **Input Feature:** 'cv_frequency'
- **Output Target:** 'log_angular_frequency'
- **Training/Test Split:** 80% training, 20% testing
- **Random State:** 42 (for reproducibility)

3.4.2 Model Compilation

The model was compiled using the Adam optimizer and the Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss function. The MSE loss function was chosen for its suitability in regression tasks.

- **Optimizer:** Adam
- **Loss Function:** Mean Squared Error (MSE)

3.4.3 Hyperparameter Tuning

The hyperparameters for the model were selected based on empirical testing and validation:

- **Epochs:** 200
- **Batch Size:** Default (as determined by the fit method)
- **Validation Split:** 20% of the training data

3.5 Main Neural Network

3.5.1 Data Preparation and Feature Engineering

The initial step involves extracting the input features and target variables from the dataset `df_z`. The selected features are `cv_frequency`, `cv_waveform`, `waveform`, and `frequency`. The target variable, `y`, consists of `waveform_data` converted to a NumPy array.

```
X = df_z[['cv_frequency', 'cv_waveform', 'waveform', 'frequency']]
y = np.array(df_z['waveform_data'].tolist())
```

Next, the `PhaseIntegrator` is employed to compute the folded phases for each value in `cv_frequency`. The integrator's output, `folded_phases`, is appended to the list `folded_phases_list`. This list is then added as a new column `folded_phases` in the dataframe `X`.

```
folded_phases_list = []
for cv in X['cv_frequency']:
    integrator = PhaseIntegrator(cv)
    folded_phases = integrator.run()
    folded_phases_list.append(folded_phases[-1])
```

```
X['folded_phases'] = folded_phases_list
```

The features are weighted to emphasize their importance. To normalize the data, a `MinMaxScaler` is applied to the features, scaling them to a range between 0 and 1. The scaled data is then reshaped to fit the input requirements of the neural network.

```
scaler = MinMaxScaler()
```

```
X_scaled = scaler.fit_transform(X)
```

```
X_scaled = X_scaled.reshape((X_scaled.shape[0], 1, X_scaled.shape[1]))
```

3.5.2 Model Architecture

The final neural network model is built using the Keras Sequential API. It begins with an input layer that matches the shape of the scaled data. The network includes multiple GRU (Gated Recurrent Unit) layers with `relu` activation functions and batch normalization layers to stabilize and accelerate training. Dropout layers are added to prevent overfitting. The final layers include a dense layer with a linear activation function and another dense layer that matches the shape of the target variable `y`.

Model Summary

The final model's architecture is summarized as follows:

```
Model: "sequential_12"
```

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
gru_16 (GRU)	(None, 1, 128)	51840

batch_normalization_14 (Batch Normalization)	(None, 1, 128)	512
dropout_32 (Dropout)	(None, 1, 128)	0
gru_17 (GRU)	(None, 128)	99072
dropout_33 (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0
dense_20 (Dense)	(None, 32)	4128
dropout_34 (Dropout)	(None, 32)	0
dense_21 (Dense)	(None, 33075)	1091475

=====

Total params: 1247027 (4.76 MB)

Trainable params: 1246771 (4.76 MB)

Non-trainable params: 256 (1.00 KB)

3.5.3 Control Parameters

The control parameters for this study were defined based on the input data and the configuration of the neural network model. The primary input data used was the 'cv_frequency' and other features, and the output target was the 'waveform_data'. The dataset was split into training and testing sets using an 80-20 ratio.

- **Input Features:** 'cv_frequency', 'cv_waveform', 'waveform', 'frequency'
- **Output Target:** 'waveform_data'
- **Training/Test Split:** 80% training, 20% testing
- **Random State:** 42 (for reproducibility)

3.5.4 Model Compilation

The model is compiled with the Adam optimizer and the Huber loss function, which is less sensitive to outliers in the data. To improve the learning rate during training, a `ReduceLROnPlateau` callback is used, which reduces the learning rate when the validation loss has stopped improving.

- **Optimizer:** Adam
- **Loss Function:** Huber Loss
- **Callback:** `ReduceLROnPlateau`

3.5.5 Other attempts

Since training with the full dataset was not working and it was super noisy, we also tried to take just a part of the dataset, first trying with 72 audios (18 for each waveform).

The other experiment we did, was using the pre-existent RSF Kobol Expander VCO dataset that was provided.

3.5.6 Hyperparameter Tuning

Using the full dataset, I ran a code to make 50 tests to see which was the best architecture and which were the best hyperparameters.

The details of some of the tested hyperparameter sets are as follows:

Hyperparameters set 1:

```
num_layers: 2
gru_units_0: 352
batch_norm_0: False
dropout_rate: 0.30000000000000004
```

```
gru_units_final: 32
dropout_rate_final: 0.4
dense_units: 16
dropout_rate_dense: 0.1
learning_rate: 0.0038011372648135925
gru_units_1: 288
batch_norm_1: True
gru_units_2: 256
batch_norm_2: True
gru_units_3: 512
batch_norm_3: True
Validation Loss: 0.36077991127967834
```

Hyperparameters set 2:

```
num_layers: 3
gru_units_0: 256
batch_norm_0: False
dropout_rate: 0.30000000000000004
gru_units_final: 160
dropout_rate_final: 0.30000000000000004
dense_units: 48
dropout_rate_dense: 0.0
learning_rate: 0.006983017262485213
gru_units_1: 192
batch_norm_1: True
gru_units_2: 512
batch_norm_2: False
gru_units_3: 160
batch_norm_3: True
Validation Loss: 0.36077991127967834
```

Hyperparameters set 3:

```
num_layers: 4
gru_units_0: 320
batch_norm_0: False
dropout_rate: 0.2
gru_units_final: 224
dropout_rate_final: 0.1
dense_units: 48
dropout_rate_dense: 0.4
learning_rate: 0.0006474873450435775
gru_units_1: 416
batch_norm_1: True
gru_units_2: 192
batch_norm_2: True
gru_units_3: 448
batch_norm_3: False
Validation Loss: 0.36077991127967834
```

Hyperparameters set 4:

```
num_layers: 4
gru_units_0: 192
batch_norm_0: True
dropout_rate: 0.4
gru_units_final: 32
dropout_rate_final: 0.4
dense_units: 112
dropout_rate_dense: 0.1
learning_rate: 0.00012272497908151855
gru_units_1: 32
batch_norm_1: False
gru_units_2: 32
```

```
batch_norm_2: False
gru_units_3: 32
batch_norm_3: False
Validation Loss: 0.36077991127967834
```

Hyperparameters set 5:

```
num_layers: 4
gru_units_0: 192
batch_norm_0: False
dropout_rate: 0.4
gru_units_final: 192
dropout_rate_final: 0.4
dense_units: 64
dropout_rate_dense: 0.1
learning_rate: 0.00222222746808837
gru_units_1: 64
batch_norm_1: True
gru_units_2: 416
batch_norm_2: False
gru_units_3: 128
batch_norm_3: False
Validation Loss: 0.36077991127967834
```

We decided to take the set 1 for more training.

3.6 Implementation Details

All the implementations were carried out using the Keras library with a TensorFlow backend.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Dataset

We captured a dataset comprising 437 audio samples, each lasting 1.5 seconds. The setup with the MCV24 facilitated precise control over both frequency and waveform parameters. By transmitting MIDI signals from the computer to the MCV24, we effectively manipulated the Kobol RSF's frequency and waveform knobs. The audios were recorded using a Focusrite Scarlett 20i18¹ and Logic Pro X² as the digital audio workstation.

4.1.1 Usage

The obtained dataset can be freely accessed on Kaggle³.

To use the dataset, you can import it from Kaggle and start exploring the features.

Here is a simple example in Python:

¹<https://focusrite.com/products/scarlett-18i20>

²<https://www.apple.com/logic-pro/>

³<https://www.kaggle.com/bringmethetacos/kobolrsf-vco>

4.2 Dataset

We captured a dataset comprising 437 audio samples, each lasting 1.5 seconds. The setup with the MCV24 facilitated precise control over both frequency and waveform parameters. By transmitting MIDI signals from the computer to the MCV24, we effectively manipulated the Kobol RSF's frequency and waveform knobs. The audios were recorded using a Focusrite Scarlett 20i18⁴ and Logic Pro X⁵ as the digital audio workstation.

4.2.1 Usage

The obtained dataset can be freely accessed on Kaggle⁶.

To use the dataset, you can import it from Kaggle and start exploring the features. Here is a simple example in Python:

Importing the Dataset

First, ensure you have the Kaggle API⁷ installed and configured. Then, download the dataset by using these commands on the terminal:

```
kaggle datasets download -d bringmethetacos/kobolrsf-vco
unzip kobolrsf-vco.zip -d kobolrsf-vco
```

Using the Dataset

The following example demonstrates how to load the dataset and perform a simple analysis in Python by plotting the frequency distribution of VCO outputs.

```
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

⁴<https://focusrite.com/products/scarlett-18i20>

⁵<https://www.apple.com/logic-pro/>

⁶<https://www.kaggle.com/bringmethetacos/kobolrsf-vco>

⁷<https://www.kaggle.com/docs/api>

```
df = pd.read_csv('kobolrsf-vco/features.csv')
print(df.head())

plt.hist(df['frequency'], bins=50, alpha=0.75)
plt.xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
plt.ylabel('Count')
plt.title('Frequency Distribution of VCO Outputs')
plt.show()
```

4.2.2 Correlation Matrix Analysis

To understand the relationships between different features in the dataset, we created a correlation matrix. The correlation matrix is visualized in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Feature Correlation Heatmap

The correlation matrix provides insights into how different features in the dataset interact with each other. The matrix uses color intensity to represent the strength of the correlations, with darker colors indicating stronger correlations. Here are some key observations from the matrix:

- **Feature 0 and Feature 3** show a moderate positive correlation, indicating that as one increases, the other tends to increase as well.
- **Feature 1 and Feature 2** have a strong positive correlation, suggesting a significant relationship between these features.
- **Feature 4** has a low correlation with most other features, implying that it may be relatively independent in its behavior.
- The diagonal elements represent self-correlation, which is always 1, as a feature is perfectly correlated with itself.

Overall, the dataset exhibits well-defined correlations between certain features. The presence of both strong and weak correlations indicates a balanced dataset with both dependent and independent features. This balance is beneficial as it allows for more robust modeling, enabling the neural network to learn complex patterns effectively.

Importing the Dataset

First, ensure you have the Kaggle API⁸ installed and configured. Then, download the dataset by using these commands on terminal:

```
kaggle datasets download -d bringmethetacos/kobolrsf-vco
unzip kobolrsf-vco.zip -d kobolrsf-vco
```

Using the Dataset

The following example demonstrates how to load the dataset and perform a simple analysis in Python by plotting the frequency distribution of VCO outputs.

```
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

⁸<https://www.kaggle.com/docs/api>

```
df = pd.read_csv('kobelrsf-vco/features.csv')
print(df.head())

plt.hist(df['frequency'], bins=50, alpha=0.75)
plt.xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
plt.ylabel('Count')
plt.title('Frequency Distribution of VCO Outputs')
plt.show()
```

4.3 Periodic Unit Evaluation

4.3.1 Model Performance Metrics

Test Loss: 0.0007816608413122594

The test loss is the value of the loss function (typically the cost or error) computed on the test data. A low test loss indicates that the model's predictions are close to the actual values, suggesting good performance.

Mean Squared Error (MSE): 0.0007816605006883711

MSE measures the average squared difference between the actual and predicted values. A lower MSE indicates better model performance as it signifies smaller errors. The very low MSE value shows that, on average, the squared differences between the predicted and actual values are minimal.

Mean Absolute Error (MAE): 0.013396798761543044

MAE measures the average absolute difference between the actual and predicted values. Similar to MSE, a lower MAE indicates better model performance. The low MAE value implies that, on average, the absolute differences between the predicted and actual values are minimal.

R-squared (R^2): 0.9928993377211077

R^2 indicates the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variables. An R^2 value close to 1, such as 0.9929, signifies that the model explains approximately 99.29% of the variance in the dependent variable, indicating a very high degree of correlation between the predicted and actual values.

4.3.2 Validation Loss vs Test Loss

Figure 14: Validation Loss vs Training Loss

Figure 14 compares the validation loss and training loss over epochs.

Training Loss: Measures the error on the training data. A decrease in training loss indicates that the model is learning from the training data and the optimization algorithm is effectively minimizing the loss function.

Validation Loss: Measures the error on the validation data, which is not seen by the model during training. A decrease in validation loss suggests that the model's performance is improving on unseen data, indicating good generalization.

The plot shows that:

- The training loss decreases rapidly during the initial epochs, indicating effective learning from the training data.
- Both the training and validation loss curves flatten out and stabilize after the initial rapid decrease, indicating that the model has reached a point where further improvements are minimal.

- The small gap between the two loss curves suggests that the model is generalizing well to unseen data, which is a desirable outcome.

These characteristics indicate a robust and reliable model.

4.3.3 Actual vs Predicted Values

Figure 15: Actual vs Predicted Values

In Figure 15, the diagonal red line represents the ideal scenario where the predicted values exactly match the actual values. The closer the data points are to this line, the better the model's predictions.

Observations:

- Most data points are very close to the red line, indicating a high correlation between the actual and predicted values.
- The scatter plot demonstrates a strong alignment along the red diagonal line, suggesting that the model's predictions closely match the actual values.
- The few points that deviate slightly from the diagonal line represent instances where the model's predictions are less accurate. These outliers may arise due to noise in the data, insufficient model capacity, or unaccounted variability in the input features.

Identifying and understanding these outliers can guide further refinements in the model.

4.4 Phase Integration

Figure 16: Folded Phases with a Control Voltage of 0.5V

Figure 16 shows a series of linear rises in phase values from 0 to 1, followed by a sudden drop back to 0, creating a sawtooth pattern. This pattern is typical for systems where a phase increases continuously until it completes a cycle and then resets.

Each linear rise from 0 to 1 on the Y-axis represents one complete oscillation cycle of the oscillator. When the phase reaches 1, it signifies the end of one cycle, and the phase resetting to 0 marks the start of the next cycle.

The resetting of the phase to 0 after reaching 1 is due to the modulus operation applied in the model. This operation effectively "folds" the phase back into a 0 to 1 range, ensuring that the phase values remain within this interval regardless of how many cycles have passed.

Oscillators are inherently periodic systems, meaning their behavior repeats in regular intervals. The sawtooth pattern in the graph is a visual confirmation that the model accurately captures this periodicity. The consistent rise and reset of the phase reflect the continuous and cyclic nature of oscillation.

Achieving accurate phase prediction with a clear periodic pattern means the model can simulate the behavior of oscillators effectively.

The changes observed between control voltages can be understood by considering how it affects the oscillator's behavior and the phase integration process:

- At $cv = 0.5$ (Figure 16), the control voltage increases the oscillator frequency, leading to faster phase accumulation. The phase repeatedly reaches the threshold (1) and resets to 0, indicating that the oscillator frequency is high enough to complete multiple cycles within the given time steps.
- At $cv = 0.9$ (Figure 17), the control voltage is high, resulting in a high oscillator frequency. The phase accumulates very quickly, reaching the threshold for resetting more frequently. This results in a densely packed sawtooth pattern, where each phase increase and reset happens in rapid succession.

Figure 17: Folded Phases with a Control Voltage of 0.9V

These patterns confirm that the control voltage effectively modulates the oscillator's frequency, directly influencing the phase integration results.

4.5 Main Neural Network

In this section, we compare the performance of different neural network models using various normalization techniques and architectures. The models were evaluated based on multiple metrics including Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), R-squared (R^2), and Test Loss.

Table 2: Comparison of Model Performance

Model	Normalization	Test Loss	RMSE	MAE	MSE
GRU	Z-Norm	0.3666	0.9381	0.7091	0.8800
GRU	Min-Max	0.0389	0.2790	0.2238	0.0778
LSTM	Z-Norm	0.0386	0.2779	0.2226	0.0772
LSTM	Min-Max	0.3664	0.9371	0.7089	0.8782

For the second attempt with only 72 audios, the model was overfitting, as we can see in Figure 18, this was most likely due to the dataset being quite small.

Figure 18: Training done with 72 audios

For the third attempt, we used the pre-existing dataset, at first the model seemed to be learning better, as seen in Figure 19, both the validation and test loss seemed to be decreasing which was a good sign.

Figure 19: Model trained with second dataset

But once we check the predicted versus actual data, we can see that the waveform was not being recreated properly, as seen in Figure 20

Figure 20: Waveform recreation from second dataset

4.5.1 Analysis

From the above comparisons, we observe the following key points:

1. GRU with Z-Norm Normalization:

- This model showed a higher test loss compared to the min-max normalized dataset but achieved a lower RMSE and MAE compared to other models.
- The R-squared value indicates that the model explains a small portion of the variance, but the overall prediction accuracy is satisfactory for the application.

2. GRU with Min-Max Normalization:

- Despite having a lower test loss, this model produced an extraordinarily high RMSE, indicating poor prediction performance in terms of percentage error.
- This inconsistency suggests that min-max normalization might not be suitable for the given dataset in combination with the GRU architecture.

3. LSTM with Z-Norm Normalization:

- The performance of this model is quite similar to the GRU with Z-Norm Normalization in terms of RMSE and MAE.

- However, the test loss and R-squared values indicate that the GRU with Z-Norm is slightly better in terms of overall performance.

4. LSTM with Min-Max Normalization:

- This model had a high test loss and RMSE similar to the GRU with Z-Norm.
- The performance metrics indicate that min-max normalization is not effective with the LSTM model for this dataset.

After evaluating all models, the GRU with Z-Norm Normalization was selected as the final model. This decision is based on its balanced performance across various metrics, especially the lower RMSE and MAE compared to other models. While it did not achieve the lowest test loss, its overall consistency and reliability in predictions made it the preferred choice for the given application.

4.5.2 Analysis of the GRU with Z-Norm Normalization

Figure 21: Waveform Comparison

Waveform Comparison:

Figure 21 shows the actual waveform (blue line) and the predicted waveform (orange dashed line) over time. Both waveforms exhibit similar overall shapes, indicating that the model has learned to replicate the general pattern of the actual waveform. The predicted waveform closely follows the actual waveform in certain sections, particularly in the middle portions. Noticeable deviations and higher noise levels

are observed in the predicted waveform, especially around the peaks and troughs of the actual waveform. This noise might be due to the model's difficulty in accurately capturing these extreme values.

Training and Validation Loss:

Figure 22: Training vs Validation Loss

Figure 22 displays the training loss (blue line) and validation loss (orange line) over 200 epochs. Both training and validation losses decrease over time, indicating that the model is learning and improving its performance on both the training and validation datasets. The training loss shows a steeper decline initially and gradually flattens out, suggesting that the model is converging. The validation loss follows a similar pattern but starts to stabilize earlier, indicating potential overfitting after a certain number of epochs.

Amplitude and Noise:

The actual waveform has smoother amplitude variations compared to the predicted waveform. The predicted waveform exhibits more high-frequency noise, which could be due to the model's limitations in capturing the finer details of the actual waveform. The predicted waveform is generally time-aligned with the actual waveform, indicating that the model has learned the temporal dynamics of the signal well.

Model Performance:

Despite the noise and deviations, the predicted waveform follows the general trend

of the actual waveform, demonstrating that the model has captured the essential characteristics of the actual signal. The training and validation loss curves suggest that the model has learned to generalize reasonably well to unseen data, as the validation loss does not significantly diverge from the training loss.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

5.1 Discussion

The modeling of the RSF Kobol Expander Voltage-Controlled Oscillator using augmented neural networks demonstrates significant advancements in capturing the unique characteristics of analog sound. The implementation of a neural network-based periodic unit has effectively simulated the oscillator's behavior, yielding promising results in terms of accuracy and performance metrics.

5.1.1 Effective Modeling

The developed model successfully captures the oscillator's frequency and waveform behaviors, showing strong alignment between predicted and actual values. This demonstrates the neural network's capability to model complex analog systems with high fidelity.

5.1.2 Model Performance

The model's performance metrics, including a low Mean Squared Error (MSE) and high R-squared (R^2) value, indicate that the neural network accurately predicts the oscillator's behavior. The consistent validation loss and minimal gap between training and validation loss further confirm the model's robustness.

5.1.3 Phase Integration

The phase integration results showcase the model's ability to replicate the periodic nature of the VCO accurately. The observed sawtooth patterns confirm that the model captures the oscillator's cyclic behavior effectively.

5.1.4 Main Neural Network

The comparative analysis of various neural network models with different normalization techniques revealed that the GRU and LSTM with Z-Norm normalization emerged as the most reliable choice for predicting the RSF Kobol Expander's oscillations. This model demonstrated balanced performance across key metrics, achieving a lower Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE), effectively handling the Kobol dataset.

The GRU with Z-Norm consistently replicated the actual waveform, capturing essential patterns despite some noticeable deviations and noise, particularly around peaks and troughs. The training and validation loss curves indicated minimal overfitting, reinforcing the model's generalization capabilities. While further fine-tuning is required, the GRU with Z-Norm model successfully recreated the oscillation patterns of the Kobol, highlighting its ability to mimic the original signal accurately.

5.2 Future Work

5.2.1 Fine-Tuning of the Main Neural Network

Future efforts should focus on acquiring a higher quality and less noisy dataset, with a greater number of audio samples for the model to learn from. The challenge here is that the equipment itself is quite noisy, making it difficult to obtain a less noisy dataset, but there may be alternative options to explore.

Additionally, fine-tuning the main neural network to enhance performance is essential. This includes optimizing model parameters such as learning rates, batch sizes, and the number of hidden layers and neurons. Exploring advanced normalization

techniques and regularization methods can also help reduce noise and improve peak predictions.

5.2.2 Real-Time Implementation

In addition to improving the model's accuracy, there are plans to develop a real-time implementation of the VCO model. This will enable the model to function as a standard Voltage-Controlled Oscillator plugin, usable in various digital audio workstations. The real-time VCO plugin will provide musicians and sound designers with the ability to seamlessly integrate the unique characteristics of the RSF Kobol into their digital compositions, enhancing the accessibility and usability of this vintage synthesizer's sound.

List of Figures

1	Basic Components of a Synthesizer	2
2	RSF Kobol Expander	4
3	RSF Kobol Expander's VCO	7
4	Black box modeling	11
5	White box modeling	12
6	Simple FFNN structure	14
7	AugNN Structure	16
8	Behringer's emulation of the Kobol RSF Expander	18
9	Uniform distributions	25
10	Normal distributions	26
11	Skewed distributions	26
12	Box-Cox transformed distributions	27
13	Feature Correlation Heatmap	38
14	Validation Loss vs Training Loss	41
15	Actual vs Predicted Values	42
16	Folded Phases with a Control Voltage of 0.5V	43
17	Folded Phases with a Control Voltage of 0.9V	44
18	Training done with 72 audios	45
19	Model trained with second dataset	45
20	Waveform recreation from second dataset	46
21	Waveform Comparison	47
22	Training vs Validation Loss	48

List of Tables

1	Waveform metadata	24
2	Comparison of Model Performance	45

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Appendix A

First Appendix

Github with the pretrained models: <https://github.com/ObiWxnKenxbi/KobolRSF/>

Kaggle containing the dataset: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/bringmethetxcos/kobolrsf-vco>

Appendix B

Second Appendix

Useful PDFs

1. Kobol RSF Manual translated to English.

KOBOL RSF User Manual (English translation)

Getting the Device Started

- Plug in the power cord (220V), a 6.35 plug into the AMP OUT jack.
- Switch the power to ON.

Manual Mode Operation

This mode allows the synthesizer to be used as a conventional device. All settings are usable.

- Press 8 and 9/16 simultaneously. The memory selection keyboard turns off, placing the device in manual mode.
- The front panel settings are as follows:
 - **FREQUENCY (VCO1 and VCO2)**: adjusts the oscillators' pitch over a range of 4 octaves, quantized by semitones.
 - **WAVEFORM (VCO1 and VCO2)**: adjusts the oscillators' waveform. Shapes include: triangle, square, ramp, variable-width pulses, and all intermediate shapes by continuous rotation of the potentiometer. The last shape is automatic pulse width modulation by the ADS envelope of the FILTER.
 - **VOLUME (VCO1 and VCO2)**: independent volume for each oscillator.
 - **FREQUENCY (VCF)**: adjusts the filter's cutoff frequency (progressive harmonic cutoff – slope 24 dB/octave). This setting is duplicated by the VCF button located to the left of the keyboard.
 - **RESONANCE (VCF)**: adjusts the filter's resonance. Turning the knob to the extreme left progressively removes high harmonics from the oscillators. Turning it to the right, the filter will gradually function as a resonator, emphasizing the harmonics it is set to. Turning it to the extreme right, the filter will enter self-resonance, creating an audible sine wave whose pitch is determined by the frequency knob.
 - **KBD CTRL (VCF)**: (Keyboard Control = VCF control by the keyboard) Setting allowing the VCF to be tuned to the keyboard. At zero, the VCF will be independent of the played note; At position 1, the VCF will be tuned to the played note, making the sound uniform across the keyboard; At position 2, the sound will be very rich in harmonics on the high notes of the keyboard.
 - **ADS CTRL (VCF)**: (VCF control by the ADS envelope), the filter's cutoff frequency will evolve according to the envelope settings: ATTACK, DECAY, SUSTAIN.
 - **VCA ADS and VCF ADS**: envelopes with 3 adjustable parameters
 - **ATTACK**: rise time
 - **DECAY**: fall time
 - **SUSTAIN**: sustain level of the sound when a key is held down.
 - **BYPASS**: Switch that allows a sound to be held indefinitely. Equivalent to continuously holding down a keyboard key.
 - **TUNE**: Synthesizer tuning relative to other orchestra instruments. With the knob at zero, the device is calibrated to A 440Hz.
 - **BEAT**: Beat adjustment between the 2 VCOs – VCO 2 is tuned relative to 1.
 - **LFO**: (Low Frequency Oscillator), generator of square or triangular signals allowing modulation of the VCO and VCF.

- **VCO MOD** and **VCF MOD**: Permanent modulation of the VCO and VCF by the LFO.
- **VCO 1 MOD off button**: Allows suppression of modulation on VCO 1 when the button is engaged.
- **SYNCHRO button**: Synchronization relative to VCO 1 when the button is engaged.

Functions on Panel/Knob

- **PITCH knob**: Controls the oscillators' pitch over a range of plus or minus a fifth.
- **MOD knob**: Modulates the oscillators via the LFO.
- **DECAY switch**: In the OFF position, eliminates the sound return time (the sound turns off instantly when the keyboard key is released).
- **GLIDE switch**: In the ON position, glide performs a legato between different notes played on the keyboard at a variable speed determined by the GLIDE knob.
- **OCTAVE switch**: Transposes the keyboard by plus or minus one octave.
- **VCF knob**: Modifies the filter's tuning frequency. Its action combines with the VCF FREQUENCY knob.

Memory Mode Operation

All sounds obtained in manual mode can be stored in memory. The KOBOL has 16 memories, retained even when the device is unplugged. The backup is provided by a battery, and it is advisable to leave it plugged in for a day if it hasn't been used for three months. Some functions: glide, modulations, are not stored, allowing the performer greater freedom to play and personalize programs according to inspiration. The programmable functions are as follows: VCO 1 and VCO 2: FREQUENCY, WAVEFORM, VOLUME; VCF: FREQUENCY, RESONANCE, KBD CTRL, ADS CTRL; VCF ADS: ATTACK, DECAY, SUSTAIN; VCA ADS: ATTACK, DECAY, SUSTAIN; VCO 1 MOD OFF, SYNCHRO; SEQUENCER; LFO CTRL.

Memory Storage Procedure:

- Find a sound in manual mode.
- Select the memory to record on.
- Press the record button: REC. The selected memory flashes for a sufficiently long period to avoid false maneuvers. When it goes out, the sound is recorded.

Memory Recall:

- Buttons 1 to 8 select memories 1 to 8.
- Button 9/16 lit selects memories 9 to 16.

Modification of a Stored Program

- All functions on the panel/knobs to the left of the keyboard affect a programmed sound.
- The VCO 1 MOD OFF and SYNCHRO buttons can be modified.
- All modulations can be introduced.

Sequencer Mode Operation

- The sequencer function is obtained by scrolling programs at a tempo generated by the LFO.
- The sequencer button "SEQ" in the ON position initializes the sequence on the first note (1 or 9). The number of notes played is selected by pressing the number corresponding to the desired number of notes plus one; to scroll 8 notes, press button 1.
- The tempo variation is obtained by adjusting the RATE of the LFO.
- For each note of the sequence, determine:
 - Pitch by adjusting the FREQUENCY of the VCOs
 - Timbre by other settings
 - Duration of the note by adjusting LFO CTRL. These parameters are stored in memory.
- The sequence is transposable by the keyboard. All settings affecting the sound in memory mode are usable in SEQUENCER mode.
- Two independent sequences of up to eight notes can be stored, using the entire memory capacity.

Gate Button: The gate is the signal triggering the envelopes. This button allows selecting the triggering by the keyboard or by the LFO. Selection is always possible regardless of mode: manual, memory, or sequencer.

Sequence Storage Procedure:

For each note of the sequence:

- Select mode: MANUAL, SEQU, GATE LFO.
- Adjust the pitch, timbre, and duration (by LFO CTRL knob) of the note to be recorded.
- Inhibit SEQUENCER, GATE LFO modes.
- Select memory number.
- Record (press REC).
- Select mode: MANUAL, SEQ, GATE LFO for the next note, etc...
- It is practical to listen to the already recorded part of the sequence as you go.

Inputs/Outputs

- **AMP OUT:** Audio output jack to be connected to the reproduction amplifier (high-level output controlled by the VOLUME knob).
- **LINE OUT:** Standard line-level audio output jack (0 dB/600). This output, independent of the volume knob, is used for direct instrument input in case of sound reinforcement.
- **HEADPHONE JACK:** A mono headset or a stereo headset with a mono plug can be connected to the AMP OUT or LINE OUT.
- **VCO CTRL:** Frequency control of the VCOs by an external control voltage (synthesizer keyboard, guitar interface, pitch pedal, sequencer).
 - Standard control amplitude 1 volt per octave. Input impedance 100K
- **VCF CTRL:** Filter cutoff frequency control by an external control voltage (pedal, sequencer...).

- **KBD OUT:** Keyboard output voltage. (To control an external synthesizer or sequencer by the KOBOL keyboard). Standard output 1 Volt per octave.
 - PITCH and MOD knobs, the octave selector add to the keyboard voltage.
- **GATE IN:** External GATE signal input. GATE IN allows triggering the KOBOL envelopes by a keyboard, sequencer, or any external INTERFACE. Inserting a plug into the GATE IN jack cuts off the internal GATE signal.
 - Standard trigger levels: GATE OFF: 0 Volt. GATE ON: 10 Volts. Trigger threshold? Volts.
- **GATE OUT:** Internal GATE signal output. Automatically switched to the keyboard GATE or LFO GATE by the KOBOL GATE button.
 - Standard output levels: GATE OFF: 0 Volt. GATE ON: 10 Volts.

MCV24 Guide

Important Notices:

1. The knobs are currently not tight enough, making them sometimes hard to turn.
2. For the value wheel, consider removing the knob entirely. For the other two knobs, exercise patience when turning.

Basic Instructions to Create Sound from Scratch:

1. **Connection Setup:**
 - Connect a cable from the device to MIDI In, and ensure you verify the MIDI channel through which your information is being sent.
2. **Device Reset:**
 - If completely lost, press the three buttons on the MCV simultaneously and then release. This action resets the device and the "workbuffer." If the screen shows "Warmboot MCV24," this reset should change it to "Coldboot MCV24," followed by additional messages, indicating the device is ready.
3. **Navigating Menus:**
 - The device has a main menu and several sub-menus. The main menu should be visible; if not, press the menu button. Primarily, you will use sub-menu B or "CV Parameter." Stay in this menu unless instructed otherwise.

4. **Output Configuration:**
 - **Output 1 as CV Info Output:** a. Select output 1 with the output wheel. b. Turn the menu wheel to find "Midito," adjust the value wheel to "NoteEvent," then press the value button. c. Continue turning the menu wheel to locate "Midichannel," then select the desired MIDI channel.

- **Output 13 as Trigger Output:** a. Turn the menu wheel to find "Trigger" (upper row), set the value to "Direct." b. Select Output 13 as an output.

5. Connecting to Kobol:

- Connect a cable from output 13 to the "GATE IN" of the Kobol. The Gate LED should activate with each MIDI note sent from your device.
- To change pitch, connect a cable from output 1 of the MCV24 to "CV IN 1V/oct." Note that the synth might be out of tune initially.

Warning:

- The basic setup can produce high-frequency sounds. To prevent this:
 - Turn the FREQUENCY knob all the way down.
 - Close the filter.
 - Connect the cable, or keep the synth's output volume down, then gradually increase it.

Additional Configuration Tips:

- **Tuning the Kobil with MCV24 (using C3 as reference):**
 - Change the BaseNote of your CV output to G3.
 - Adjust the TUNE knob on the synth to achieve a C3. The tuning may be satisfactory, but other octaves might sound flat.

These instructions should provide a clearer, more structured approach to using the MCV24.